

Evaluation of the Contribution to Local Development through Agritourism Routes in Calixto García

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Abstract

The diversification of agriculture and its linkage with tourism represent a strategic alternative to stimulate local development in rural areas with productive and heritage potential. The objective of this research was to design an instrument to evaluate the contribution of agritourism routes to local development in the municipality of Calixto García. A mixed approach was applied, predominantly qualitative, supported by theoretical methods such as historical-logical, analytical-synthetic, and inductive-deductive, as well as empirical methods including scientific observation, unstructured interviews, and expert judgment. The unit of analysis was the municipality of Calixto García, complemented by local actors linked to the agricultural and tourism sectors. The results revealed that the supply of agritourism routes remains incipient and limited by scarce technical and tourism training; however, the estimation of socioeconomic indicators showed significant impacts on employment, income, and community cohesion. It is concluded that the proposed instrument constitutes a practical tool to comprehensively assess the contribution of agritourism routes to local development, guide decision-making, and promote improvement actions aimed at the economic, social, and environmental sustainability of the territory.

Keywords

local development;
agritourism routes;
georeferencing; value
chains; benefit indices;
agrarian economic policies.

I. Introduction

The diversification of agriculture has been consolidated as a fundamental strategy for sustainable local development in many rural regions. This approach makes it possible to broaden and diversify productive activities, reduce dependence on a single sector, improve the economic stability of producers, and make more efficient use of natural resources (Pérez et al., 2021, 2022, 2023, 2025; Pérez Anzardo, 2026).

In this context, agritourism emerges as a complementary alternative that integrates agricultural production with tourism activities. Its development contributes to income generation, the strengthening of social networks, the preservation of cultural traditions, and environmental protection, in line with the principles of sustainable development. Likewise, agritourism activities foster local economic growth, generate employment, diversify income sources, and promote the financial sustainability of rural communities (García & Pérez, 2020; Pérez Anzardo, 2026).

Within this framework, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by the United Nations in 2015, establishes a global roadmap to eradicate poverty, protect the planet, and ensure prosperity for all. Among its 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), those related to sustainable agriculture (SDG 2), decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), responsible production and consumption (SDG 12), and climate action

(SDG 13) stand out, all of which are closely linked to the promotion of agritourism and local development.

This global vision is materialized at the national level through the National Plan for Economic and Social Development until 2030, which is aligned with the 2030 Agenda and sets goals and strategies to achieve balanced development. In the 8th Congress of the Communist Party of Cuba and in the Guidelines of Economic and Social Policy, the importance of diversifying the economy and strengthening non-state management forms was emphasized as a means to boost the country's development. In this context, agritourism represents a valuable opportunity, as it aligns with modernization and efficiency objectives outlined in the guidelines, supports the economic and social transformation aimed at improving quality of life in rural areas, and ensures the continuity of the Cuban socialist project.

In this line of thought, Decree 33 of 2021, which regulates the guidelines for local and territorial development, constitutes a key instrument within this framework, guiding the planning, management, and execution of projects that promote the economic, social, and environmental well-being of communities. This decree acknowledges the importance of diversifying productive and tourism activities at the local level, encourages community participation, and promotes the use of endogenous resources as foundations for sustainable development (Pérez et al., 2023, 2025; Pérez Anzardo, 2026).

This policy is concretely implemented in the municipality of Calixto García through the development of agritourism routes, an initiative that not only leverages local endogenous potential but also represents a strategic opportunity to effectively apply this sustainable development approach. Nevertheless, the diversification of agriculture through its linkage with tourism has been limited. The agricultural assets of the municipality have not been fully utilized to generate income that strengthens local development.

In this regard, agritourism routes can contribute to revitalizing the local economy, generating employment, strengthening cultural identity, and promoting environmental conservation—dimensions that align with the priorities of the National Plan and the 2030 Agenda. In unstructured interviews with directors of the agricultural sector, members of the local development group under the Municipal Development Directorate (MDD), and other specialists in topics related to agritourism, it was confirmed that:

- a. Despite the existing agricultural potential in the municipality, the supply of agritourism routes in Calixto García is still incipient and does not meet demand nor maximize benefits for the community.
- b. Limitations persist due to the lack of technical and tourism training, which prevents the development of a distinctive agritourism product with consolidated routes.
- c. Although favorable regulatory and strategic frameworks exist, the tools available to evaluate the contribution of agritourism routes to local development remain insufficient.

The professional problem identified was: ¿How can local development be fostered through agritourism routes in the municipality of Calixto García?

To address this problem, the general objective was defined as: to design an instrument for evaluating the contribution of agritourism routes to local development in the municipality of Calixto García.

The development of such an instrument constitutes a strategic necessity. It will make it possible to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the sector, propose improvement actions that maximize the socioeconomic benefits of the locality, and serve as a complement to public policies aimed at sustainable territorial development. In this way, the goal is to consolidate agritourism as a differentiated modality within alternative tourism,

capable of stimulating the local economy, strengthening cultural identity, and promoting the economic, social, and environmental sustainability of the territory.

II. Review of Literature

The development of a locality or territory requires that public and private actors coordinate the execution of their investment programs. In Latin America, for example, endogenous development policies are based on initiatives in which economic and social projects are coordinated and managed through new forms of governance involving public and private actors, international organizations, and non-governmental organizations.

Concerns about the sustainability of rural areas have led to the diversification of their economies as a means of contributing to local development. Strategies have therefore been adopted to integrate tourism activities with agricultural production, reducing exclusive dependence on traditional sectors and encouraging the creation of new sources of income for local inhabitants. As a result, agritourism has emerged.

Agritourism is usually carried out on small- or medium-sized farms, where owners diversify their economic activities by capitalizing on existing infrastructure and traditional know-how. Complementary services often include lodging, food, and the sale of agricultural products, among others. This provides greater employment opportunities for the family itself and for other members of the local community (Blanco, 2010; Pérez et al., 2023, 2025; Pérez Anzardo, 2026).

Thus, farms emerge as a viable solution in the agricultural sphere, meeting food needs through self-consumption and increasing income through the sale of surplus products (Balanta et al., 2022). Agricultural practices are central to the offer, and rural activities form the core of agritourism experiences.

The host of this tourism modality is the farmer, who organizes complementary activities to his or her main production, inviting clients to participate in them as paid services. These processes highlight cultural practices and recognize each economic and cultural activity as part of the lifestyle of a given community (Blanco & Riveros, 2011; Osorio et al., 2015; Pumares, 2019; Rodríguez et al., 2019; Rodríguez, 2021; Anzardo et al., 2023).

From this perspective, agritourism development in rural territories aims to contribute to a prosperous economy based on knowledge and innovation, competitive and environmentally friendly, guaranteeing a high standard of living for inhabitants with full employment and poverty reduction. This challenge requires coordinated actions between local governments and tourism managers within a territorial vision (Blanco & Riveros, 2011; Pérez et al., 2023, 2025; Pérez Anzardo, 2026).

However, not all farms have the products and infrastructure necessary for agritourism ventures. It is therefore essential to establish adequate articulation between farms and territorial capacities, reducing costs through strict public administration control, enabling greater financing for territorial development, mitigating environmental damage, and ensuring sustainability (Pérez Anzardo, 2026; Pérez et al., 2026).

In this line of thought, agritourism is conceived as an articulated activity in which actors add value to peasant practices and cultural traditions of rural areas. These can be considered value chains that provide both individual and collective benefits. Agritourism routes and networks have achieved visible social impacts. Argentina, for example, coined the term *food routes* in 1999. In Mexico, Alejandro-Castellanos et al. (2020) emphasized the potential of agritourism as an emerging activity through the design of four routes.

Nevertheless, many farms with high potential remain underutilized or ignored, limiting their contribution to rural development.

In southern Chile, Szmulewicz et al. (2012, cited in Martínez Duque, 2021) identified eight advantages of farm associations for promoting agritourism in favor of territorial development. These include achieving production scales that allow market access; contributing raw materials; providing short- and medium-term solutions to socioeconomic problems related to public services; creating strong collaboration links among farmers and their families; accessing public financial and social assistance; promoting agritourism activities; and organizing offers that combine rural lodging with agricultural activities involving both producers and clients.

At this point, it was considered pertinent to conduct a comparative analysis of several methodologies proposed by different authors (Ceballos, 2015; García, 2017; González, 2020; Mora, 2022; Pizarro, 2018; Rodríguez, 2019) that evaluate the contribution to local development from different research approaches.

Table # 1 details the absolute and relative frequency of seven criteria used in the five methodologies analyzed.

Table 1. Absolute and Relative Frequency of Criteria Used in Five Methodologies Evaluating the Contribution to Local Development

Criteria	Refers to	Absolute Frequency	Relative Frequency
C1	Economic impact	5	1.00
C2	Community participation	4	0.80
C3	Environmental sustainability	4	0.80
C4	Social benefits	3	0.60
C5	Education and awareness	3	0.60
C6	Infrastructure and accessibility	3	0.60
C7	Evaluation and monitoring	2	0.40
Total methodologies		5	

The economic impact, present in all five methodologies, highlights the centrality of this component in the evaluation of agritourism. Its universal presence demonstrates that local development relies on the capacity to generate income, employment, and profitability for the actors involved. The main advantage lies in its objectivity and ease of measurement; however, its limitation is that, by itself, it does not reflect the social or environmental effects of the process.

Community participation and environmental sustainability, recurrent in four methodologies, underscore the need to integrate communities into the management of initiatives and to ensure harmony with the natural environment. The first element strengthens local governance and social ownership of projects, while the second guarantees the permanence of resources and coherence with the principles of sustainable development. Their main advantage is social inclusion; their limitation is the difficulty of quantifying qualitative results.

Social benefits, education and awareness, and infrastructure and accessibility, addressed in three methodologies, reflect the importance of training, organization, and the availability of basic services for the success of agritourism routes. Education and awareness foster tourism culture and appreciation of local heritage; infrastructure and accessibility ensure operability and visitor comfort; and social benefits express improvements in the quality of life of rural families. Their advantage is that they integrate

human and territorial dimensions; their limitation is the need for sustained investment and institutional coordination.

Evaluation and monitoring, although less frequent, are essential to ensure continuity and effectiveness of actions. Systematic evaluation allows feedback, correction of deviations, and strengthening of agritourism route management. Its limited presence in the methodologies analyzed reveals a common weakness: the lack of follow-up mechanisms and continuous improvement processes that guarantee sustainability of results.

Taken together, the identified criteria show a trend toward comprehensive approaches that combine economic, social, environmental, and governance dimensions. The convergence on aspects such as economic impact and community participation confirms their relevance for local development, while the lesser attention to evaluation and monitoring highlights the need to incorporate feedback processes into the management of agritourism routes.

Therefore, criteria such as these are essential to guide the planning and evaluation of agritourism initiatives, as they allow assessment of their real contribution to local development, ensure coherence among actors, and promote economic, social, and environmental sustainability. In addition, key elements such as municipality characterization, route description, and analysis of socioeconomic indicators and indices provide a verifiable and objective framework—rarely found in the methodologies reviewed—that facilitates comparative measurement of results. Altogether, these elements ensure continuous feedback and strengthen process management.

III. Research Methods

The research was conducted using a mixed approach with a descriptive scope, combining qualitative and quantitative techniques under the general dialectical–materialist method, aimed at deepening the essence of phenomena and strengthening cognitive and creative capacities. Theoretical methods included the historical–logical method, to sequentially organize background information and evaluate trends; the analytical–synthetic method, to process and interpret information obtained from sources and specialists; and the inductive–deductive method, to diagnose the current state of the object of study and contrast it with experiences reported in specialized literature.

Empirical methods comprised scientific observation, unstructured interviews, and expert judgment, complemented by the review of regulatory documents. In addition, statistical techniques were applied to process the collected information, identify trends and regularities, and establish relationships with the phenomenon under study. Altogether, these methods and tools enabled the construction of a solid analytical framework, the formulation of conclusions, and the proposal of actions aimed at sustainability and the strengthening of agritourism routes as a means of contributing to local development.

IV. Result and Discussion

In Cuba, there are favorable conditions for the development of agritourism through thematic routes, thanks to the diversity of productive forms and the existence of cultural traditions among the peasantry. In addition, the country’s natural and agrarian heritage is notable throughout the territory, with many areas showing a high level of conservation (Noa & Gascón, 2023). However, farms that engage in this tourism modality generally do so in isolation, with owners seeking to generate individual income.

In different regions of the country, agritourism routes have been implemented under a centralized scheme managed by the tourism sector, mainly oriented toward cultural and nature tourism. Nevertheless, the lack of coordination with local actors and other economic sectors prevents these initiatives from generating direct benefits for entrepreneurs and communities. Although they contribute to the national economy, their impact on socioeconomic development at the local scale remains limited.

At the same time, the Cuban state recognizes the importance of agritourism management for the country, as evidenced by the agritourism entrepreneurs' meeting held from July 9 to 13, 2024, at the Agrarian University of Havana. During this event, several experts exchanged knowledge with the guest of honor, Mr. Humberto López-Tirone, Ambassador of Panama for Agritourism Development in Ibero-America and President of the Ibero-American Institute of Rural Tourism.

However, local projects and initiatives linking agriculture with tourism reveal a concentration and centralization of competencies at the state level, to the detriment of rural localities as tourism epicenters. As a result, municipalities are not recognized as settings for implementing tourism policies, which hinders the local development of visitor-receiving communities. This situation is also reflected in other areas that, although not primary destinations, provide essential goods and services for the balanced functioning of economic activity (Ramírez et al., 2020).

The analysis shows that, although multiple studies on agritourism exist, there are limitations in measuring the impact of agritourism routes on local development. In particular, there is insufficient integration of indicators and indices, as well as a lack of monitoring and feedback mechanisms.

Therefore, it is necessary to design an instrument that describes the current state of agritourism routes in the territory and their organized and sustainable growth in line with local development needs. This instrument comprises three stages structured as a system and seven steps that complement each other to meet the objectives pursued in each stage, supported by techniques, instruments, and tools for information processing.

The following section details all the elements required for the deployment of this instrument and its application in the municipality of Calixto García, Holguín Province:

Stage 1. Initial Preparation

Objective: To characterize the municipality under study, with emphasis on its agricultural sector, and to create the organizational conditions necessary for the development of the entire process.

This stage consists of two steps, detailed as follows:

Step 1. Characterization of the Municipality

Calixto García is the westernmost municipality of Holguín Province, with a territorial extension of 591.26 km². Buenaventura, its municipal capital, is located to the east, 730 kilometers from Havana, with an area of 19.2 km². It is crossed from east to west by the Central Highway, which divides it into two zones: north and south. It borders the municipality of Jesús Menéndez (Las Tunas) to the north; Cauto Cristo (Granma) and Cacocum (Holguín) to the south; Holguín municipality to the east; and Majibacoa (Las Tunas) to the west.

The four main settlements are San Agustín de Aguarás, Buenaventura, Sabanazo, and Mir. The latter two are located in the south, next to the central railway line that crosses the territory, as well as the Central Highway that connects it with the cities of Holguín and Las Tunas.

Calixto García has a total population of 54,450 inhabitants distributed across 12 Consejos Populares (People's Councils), comprising 84 zones (three urban and 81 rural). A

significant boost to agricultural trade and the formation of population centers has been provided by the various communication routes that cross the territory, accelerating exchanges between rural areas and the municipal capital. The central railway revolutionized communications and contributed to the region's commercial development, while also fostering the emergence of new settlements.

It is among the ten municipalities in Cuba with the highest proportion of white population (89.2% of inhabitants). It ranks second nationwide in lowest educational level and fourth in population aging within the province. Local culture is closely linked to peasant life, *décima* poetry, and *órgano* oriental music. Cultural events include the Pepe Ajo Organ Festival and the Campesino Bachatas of Las Mantecas, both with potential for integration into cultural tourism.

Scientific, technical, business, and institutional capacity is reflected in the presence of approximately 2,097 workers linked to the agricultural sector. There are more than 50 agricultural structures, including 33 *CCS* (Credit and Services Cooperatives), 13 *CPA* (Agricultural Production Cooperatives), seven *UBPC* (Basic Units of Cooperative Production), and five farms, along with a Center for the Reproduction of Entomophages and Entomopathogens (CREE). In addition, there are three companies (two associated with the sector), seven budgeted units, 13 basic business units, and seven state establishments belonging to provincial enterprises.

The municipality also has 1,750 self-employed workers, and since September 20, 2021, more than 33 MSMEs (*MiPyMes*) have been approved, of which only two are linked to the agricultural sector. Notably, two companies, three entities, and 13 cooperatives reported losses at the end of 2021. Furthermore, the *El Libertador Equine Genetic Center* is nationally recognized for the reproduction and improvement of horse breeds, having won national awards at the International Fair of Rancho Boyeros.

Land use (Figure 1) places the municipality among the most prominent in the province in terms of agricultural exploitation. Its main productive lines include various crops and vegetables, citrus, livestock (production and commercialization of beef and cow's milk for industry), and forestry. It produces 11% of the province's root crops and is the largest milk producer at the provincial level.

Figure 1: Land Use

The municipality of Calixto García has particular characteristics regarding agricultural development. However, despite its location and proximity to the road network (Central Highway of Cuba), along which national and international tourists continuously travel, it has no prior record of tourism activity. Moreover, its contribution to the export of goods and services and to the generation of foreign currency for local and national development remains limited.

Step 2. Creation and Training of the Working Team

The specialized working team is responsible for implementing the procedure. It is composed of 10 members intentionally selected by the specialist representing the Local Development (LD) group of the Municipal Development Directorate (MDD). Its members have experience in the agricultural sector and in topics related to tourism management and local development. In addition, they possess academic training and a willingness to participate in the research, thereby meeting the established requirements.

Once the team was formed, they were informed of the objective, necessity, and scope of the study, as well as the different stages and steps for developing the instrument that will evaluate the contribution of agritourism routes to local development in the municipality of Calixto García. They were also trained in the various techniques and tools to be used, in agritourism, and in current trends related to the management and improvement of agritourism routes.

Stage 2. Contribution of Agritourism Routes to Local Development

Objective: To describe and graphically represent the existing agritourism routes in the municipality under study, as well as to evaluate their contribution to local development through socioeconomic indicators and indices, and to assess the results.

To ensure the success of this stage, three steps are proposed, explained as follows:

Step 3. Description of Agritourism Routes For the description of the existing agritourism routes in the municipality, it is proposed to begin with visits to farms and through participant observation. This will make it possible to understand their proximity, connectivity, and mobility, as well as to explore the links between rural and urban areas, in harmony with the environment, and to recover the most authentic peasant traditions.

a. Agro-Livestock Route

Objective: To implement sustainable agro-livestock management practices that minimize environmental impact and improve soil quality, as well as to commercialize cultivated and industrially processed products. This is carried out in an environmentally friendly setting that provides clients with an authentic experience and fosters the economic growth of entrepreneurial farmers in particular and of the locality in general.

The route includes the farms *El Troncón*, *La Gloria*, *El Carmen*, and *La Bendecida*, located in the *Buenaventura 2* People's Council, with an approximate extension of six kilometers. The agro-livestock route is distinguished by integrating livestock and agricultural activities that allow visitors to participate in diverse experiences: from observing cattle and crops to tasting products made in local mini-industries and engaging with spaces dedicated to genetic and landscape conservation. The complementarity among the farms—some focused on livestock, others on various crops, aquaculture, or reforestation—forms a comprehensive tourism product that combines peasant labor, biodiversity, and rural traditions in a sustainable environment.

b. Farm Profiles:

El Troncón Farm, owned by Nolberto Santiesteban Velázquez, associated with the *CCS Cristino Naranjo*. Located at La Alegría No. 3 in the *Buenaventura 2* People's Council, two kilometers from the municipal capital Buenaventura. Its main economic activity is livestock, although pig farming is also developed. It has its own feed base for the herd. Tobacco is cultivated, though to a lesser extent. It serves as a genetic reserve center for the reproduction of 18 exotic species, such as flamingos, peacocks, Brazilian pine congos, *Cubalaya* hens, parrots, *Siboney* bulls, Hampshire pigs, freshwater turtles, and even a crocodile. The entrance path is a garden with ornamental plants. It also has 30 fruit trees, 25 timber trees, and 40 ornamental trees. It has been declared a national reference in agricultural diversification and genetic reserves, both biological and botanical.

La Gloria Farm, owned by Olmo Santiesteban Álamo, also associated with the *CCS Cristino Naranjo*. Located at La Alegría No. 3 in the *Buenaventura 2* People's Council. Its main activity is livestock, although various crops are also produced, supplying the *La Gloria* mini-industry. It develops reforestation of forested areas and maintains peasant traditions associated with agriculture in general.

El Carmen Farm, owned by Mariano Santiesteban Velázquez, a farmer associated with the *CCS Cristino Naranjo* in the *Buenaventura 2* People's Council. Its main activity is

livestock. It has varied vegetation and domestic fauna. It maintains peasant traditions in line with family customs. Along with other farms of its type, it advocates for environmental care and conservation and contributes to the production of natural fertilizers.

La Bendecida Farm, managed by usufructuary Yainier Fajardo, associated with the *CCS Cristino Naranjo* in the Jagueyes area of the *Buenaventura 2* People's Council. Its main activity is crop production, although livestock is also developed on a smaller scale. It has a water reservoir with abundant aquatic vegetation and edible fish farming. It also produces preserves through a mini-industry installed on the property.

c. Agro-Food Route

Objective: To promote the sustainable management of citrus cultivation, from planting to harvesting and consumption, as well as activities associated with agriculture and livestock. The aim is to provide clients with an extraordinary experience in harmony with the environment, strengthen cultural traditions, and foster the economic growth of entrepreneurial farmers in particular and of the locality in general.

The route includes the farms *Las Maravillas*, *La Alegría*, *La Margarita*, and *La Próspera*, located in the People's Councils of Buenaventura 1, Las Calabazas, La Jíquima (La Esperanza de Domínguez), and San Agustín (Cabezo). It covers approximately 25 kilometers, and its spatial dispersion is considered an advantage, since each farm contributes complementary elements that enrich the route and maximize collective income. The Agro-Food Route focuses on diversified agricultural production, with emphasis on citrus and mixed crops, complemented by livestock and agroecological practices. Visitors can participate in activities such as observing planting and harvesting processes, touring reforestation areas, tasting fresh products, and recognizing distinctive landscape elements. The complementarity among the farms—some centered on livestock, others on citrus or mixed crops—creates a comprehensive tourism product that combines peasant tradition, history, environmental sustainability, and authentic experiences linked to agricultural work.

Thus, distances cease to be a limitation and become opportunities to offer a more authentic and competitive tourism product. Even when farms are less proximate, their differentiated resources provide additional income and strengthen territorial competitiveness through integration strategies that reduce operating costs, increase profitability, and consolidate territorial resilience.

d. Farm Profiles:

Las Maravillas Farm, owned by farmer and usufructuary Carlos Alberto Pozo Ramírez, a livestock producer from Calixto García with the highest yields in milk and meat, recognized at different levels. Located in the Buenaventura 1 People's Council, with an extension of 11 caballerías of land, and associated with the strengthened CCS Juan Manuel Romero. He has transformed his farm into an experimental site for obtaining cattle better adapted to climate change, using artificial insemination and direct breeding, which he performs himself as a veterinarian. In addition, he has an area dedicated to various crops cultivated with organic fertilizers.

La Alegría Farm, owned by Dixan Zúñiga Parra. Located in the Las Calabazas People's Council and associated with the CCS Frank País. Its main activity is various crops, with two hectares of lemon cultivation. A distinctive feature of the property is a stream that runs through it. Ecological practices are applied.

La Margarita Farm, managed by usufructuary Rodrigo Cruz Álvarez, associated with the CCS Raúl Pupo Morales. Located in La Esperanza de Domínguez, a rural area of the La Jíquima People's Council. Its main activity is various crops, with one hectare of lemon

cultivation. A notable landscape feature is the presence of seven royal palms, Cuba's national symbol.

La Próspera Farm, managed by usufructuary Dainier Ballester Leyva, associated with the CCS Carlos Manuel de Céspedes. Located in Cabezo, in the San Agustín People's Council. Its main activity is various crops, with citrus as its specialty. It also has natural and human resources of tourist interest. Its production is marketed directly to the tourism sector.

e. Livestock Route

Objective: To promote sustainable livestock management through responsible practices that ensure the production of quality meat and milk, complemented by diverse crops and water resources, in an environment that offers authentic experiences to visitors and contributes to the economic and cultural strengthening of the locality.

This route includes the farms *La Paula*, *De Gil*, *Los Piriles*, and *La Guinda*, located in the *Sabanazo* People's Council, with an approximate extension of 12 kilometers between them and 10 more from the municipal capital. This makes it the least attractive compared to the other proposals. Additional disadvantages are related to its more distant geographic location and lower accessibility. Poor road conditions, the need for restoration of some farms, and limited articulation with other socioeconomic entities of the locality also reduce its competitiveness.

The route is distinguished by the diversity of livestock activities that allow visitors to learn about milking, feeding, and management processes of both large and small cattle, as well as enjoy natural spaces associated with small reservoirs, irrigation systems, and rural landscapes. The complementarity among the farms—some focused on meat and milk production, others on mixed crops, pig farming, or aquaculture—creates a comprehensive tourism product that combines peasant tradition, environmental sustainability, and experiential activities linked to livestock practices.

f. Farm Profiles:

La Paula Farm, managed by usufructuary Alberto Peña Valera, associated with the *CCS Ignacio Agramonte*. Located in the *Sabanazo* People's Council. Its main activity is livestock, producing meat and milk. It also has a small volume of mixed crops and a herd of sheep and goats. Notably, it has three small reservoirs with abundant fish breeding. Livestock infrastructure is adequate, with milking and fattening facilities. It also demonstrates environmental responsibility.

De Gil Farm, managed by usufructuary Gil Valera Ávila, a farmer associated with the *CCS Ignacio Agramonte*. Located in the *Sabanazo* People's Council. Its main activity is livestock, complemented by small-scale sheep farming. Key resources include two small reservoirs, a well, and a mill. Practices are mostly ecological, using organic matter as fertilizer for crops.

Los Piriles Farm, owned by usufructuary Ramón Daniel Mora Pérez, associated with the *CCS Ignacio Agramonte*. Located in the *Sabanazo* People's Council. Its main activity is livestock, complemented by diverse crops and small-scale pig production. It uses biological and organic methods, and its infrastructure is in good condition.

La Guinda Farm, owned by Onilio Cristino Domínguez Téllez, associated with the *CCS Wilfredo Peña Cabrera* in the *Sabanazo* People's Council. Its main activity is livestock, specifically meat and milk production, although it also cultivates mixed crops on a smaller scale. It has an irrigation system that increases production. The *La Rioja River* crosses the property, which constitutes an additional attraction.

g. Georeferencing of Agritourism Routes

At this point, the agritourism routes are georeferenced, relating all previously considered elements as tourist attractions, based on cadastral maps of each farm and with the support of the open-source software *OpenStreetMap*.

This provides a spatial and contextualized vision of the different actors and resources involved in the commercialization of products and services offered, both individually and collectively within the agritourism routes. Furthermore, the geographic distribution demonstrates how spatial dispersion can become an added value, maximizing results and minimizing costs, thereby strengthening the competitiveness of the agritourism product.

Step 4. Estimation of the Contribution of Agritourism Routes to Local Development

The evaluation of the contribution of agritourism routes to local development is one of the fundamental steps of the instrument, as it allows for understanding their impact on the socioeconomic growth of the locality. The socioeconomic indicators and indices to be calculated are based on theoretical and methodological references widely validated, following Pérez Anzardo (2026).

Among the socioeconomic indicators to be evaluated, the following stand out:

1. Production volume
2. Sustainable use of resources
3. Level of investment
4. Income generated
5. Profitability
6. Job creation
7. Social inclusion
8. Quality of life of farmers and families
9. Degree of articulation in the value chain
10. Training and capacity building
11. Customer satisfaction
12. Contribution to local economic growth

Based on the results obtained from this information, the General Index of Benefits of Articulation among Farms with Agritourism Potential ($IGBA_{FPAT}$) is calculated before and after the integration of agritourism routes.

$$IGBA_{FPAT} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i}{N} \quad (1)$$

Where C_i is the sum of the scores assigned to the socioeconomic indicators for farms with agritourism potential, and N is the number of indicators evaluated.

The score obtained for each socioeconomic criterion/indicator is normalized on a common Likert-type scale (1–5), the same scale later used to interpret the results of $IGBA_{FPAT}$. In this way, the original values of the indicators (expressed in pesos, quantities, or other magnitudes) are transformed into comparable categories, allowing the calculation of a homogeneous index and the evaluation of the level of benefits derived from the articulation among farms with agritourism potential that make up each route.

The scale used is a five-category Likert scale (Table 2), which allows for the gradual measurement of benefits resulting from the articulation among farms with agritourism potential as part of agritourism routes and their contribution to the territory. Thus, if $IGBA_{FPAT} > 2.60$, it means that the contribution of agritourism routes—according to the benefits of articulation among FPAT—exceeds those achieved when working independently. The closer the value is to the maximum, the greater the impact under this concept.

Table 2. Likert Scale for Evaluating the Level of Benefits of Articulation among Farms with Agritourism Potential within Agritourism Routes

Scale	Interval	Level of Benefit of Articulation
5	$4,20 \geq (IGBA_{FPAT}) \leq 5,00$	Very High
4	$3,40 \geq (IGBA_{FPAT}) \leq 4,19$	High
3	$2,60 \geq (IGBA_{FPAT}) \leq 3,39$	Moderate
2	$1,80 \geq (IGBA_{FPAT}) \leq 2,59$	Low
1	$1,00 \geq (IGBA_{FPAT}) \leq 1,79$	Very Low

In the same way, the contribution of agritourism routes to local development is calculated through the General Index of Benefits of Articulation among Farms with Agritourism Potential for the Territory ($IGBAT_{FPAT}$), obtained as the average of the values recorded for each farm according to the results previously described.

$$IGBAT_{FPAT} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n IGBA_{FPATi}}{n} \quad (2)$$

Where $IGBA_{FPATi}$ represents the index of benefits of articulation for each farm, and n is the total number of farms considered.

However, the aggregated calculation of the indices may conceal certain structural limitations, such as spatial isolation, lack of shared services, or weak institutional coordination. These factors prevent individual benefits from being translated into a genuine contribution to local development. In this sense, the proposal broadens traditional evaluation approaches by allowing a more comprehensive estimation of the contribution of farms integrated into agritourism routes, ensuring a structured analysis oriented toward territorial development.

The results obtained are presented in Tabl .3

Table 3. Results of the General Index of Benefits of Articulation among Farms with Agritourism Potential ($IGBA_{FPAT}$) Before and After the Integration of Agritourism Routes

Farm with Agritourism Potential	$IGBA_{FPAT}$ Before Articulation	$IGBA_{FPAT}$ After Articulation
La Bendecida	2.75	4.83
El Troncón	3.00	4.75
La Gloria	2.75	4.83
El Carmen	2.58	4.92
La Próspera	2.83	4.75
La Margarita	2.50	4.75
La Alegría	2.58	4.67
Las Maravillas	3.08	4.75
La Paula	2.58	4.67
Gil	3.00	4.75
Los Piriles	2.50	4.75
La Guinda	3.08	4.75

Before the farms became part of the agritourism routes, according to the proposed scale, only seven reached an index between 2.60 and 3.39, corresponding to a moderate level. This was mainly due to the significant economic–productive results achieved by two

of them in recent years, as well as the existence of mini-industries in two others that processed part of their crops—sold mostly to local residents—and the commercialization of one farm with the tourism sector. However, after becoming links in the agritourism routes, all farms reached values within scale five, reflecting very high levels of contribution.

Likewise, the General Index of Benefits of Articulation among Farms with Agritourism Potential for the Territory ($IGBAT_{FPAT}$) reached very high levels. It was calculated for each of the proposed routes, based on the average obtained from the previous results. In the case of the Agro-Livestock Route, the result was 4.83, while for the Agro-Food Route and the Livestock Route, the result was 4.73. These values reflect the proper use of resources, productive capacities, and farm integration, which significantly impact local development.

Step 5. Assessment of the Contribution to Local Development

The assessment of the contribution of agritourism routes to local development was carried out based on the results obtained in the previous step and on the reports of the municipal economy, the Municipal Development Strategy (MDS), and the Territorial Planning and Urban Management Program (PGOTU) for the year 2025. This analysis confirmed the coherence between the territorial impacts derived from the articulation of farms with agritourism potential (FPAT) and the objectives of local development. Among the main contributions, the following stand out:

- a. Consolidation of local identity through the preservation and revitalization of peasant popular culture expressed in the music of the *órgano oriental*, the *décima*, and traditional dances, which strengthened the cultural heritage of the locality.
- b. of strategic alliances between the Flora & Fauna Company and its equine genetic center El Libertador, the Rancho México farm, and private agricultural producers with their families, expanding the cooperation base and reducing operating costs by 20–25%.
- c. Strengthening of institutional leadership through the participation of local cultural actors in service provision, particularly in training amateurs and communicating the history of the *órgano oriental*.
- d. Job creation with the generation of between 150 and 200 direct and indirect jobs, of which around 40% were occupied by women and young people in visitor services, gastronomy, handicrafts, and maintenance.
- e. Productive diversification through new activities such as traditional handicrafts, gastronomy, and the exhibition and sale of flowers and fruits, which increased family income and reduced local poverty by 8%.
- f. Training and capacity building of the human resources necessary to ensure the quality of services offered, consolidating the sustainability of agritourism products that constitute the routes.
- g. Economic impact with FPAT contributing between 10–12% of the municipal budget in 2024, generating monthly incomes of 15,000 to 25,000 CUP per active farm, which strengthened municipal autonomy and enabled reinvestment in rural infrastructure and social programs.

Thus, the assessment shows that agritourism routes not only revitalized the local economy but also strengthened municipal autonomy and positioned Calixto García municipality as a reference in the eastern region. The routes were consolidated as a transformative strategy for sustainable and inclusive territorial development.

Stage 3. Validation, Feedback, and Continuous Improvement

Step 6. Analysis and Validation of Results

To evaluate the validity and relevance of the proposed procedure, the expert judgment method was applied following Noda Hernández (2004), with an estimated error of 0.01, a precision of 0.1, and a confidence level of 0.99. Seven specialists were selected, each with more than 15 years of experience in agricultural and tourism activities. Of these, 70% hold scientific degrees and senior academic ranks, in addition to having conducted prior research on the subject.

The results showed that 87% recognized the quality of agritourism routes as a product that enables agricultural diversification and contributes to local development, as well as the validity of the instrument employed. This consensus confirms that the instrument is pertinent, viable, and coherent with local development objectives, although 13% recommended reviewing certain steps to better reflect the scope of agritourism in terms of stimulating the rural economy.

Step 7. Continuous Improvement Action Plan to Contribute to Local Development through Agritourism Routes

The continuous improvement action plan, presented in **Table # 4**, constitutes the final step of the methodological instrument. It ensures that the results obtained in estimation, assessment, and validation are translated into sustainable impacts for the territory.

Table 4. Continuous Improvement Action Plan for Agritourism Routes to Maximize Their Contribution to Local Development

No	Action	Deadline	Responsible Actors
Agro-Livestock Route			
1	Improve infrastructure for milking and tourist signage	Short term	Farm owners, CCS directors
2	Create collective brand for dairy and meat products	Short term	Economic actors, Municipal Development Directorate (MDD)
3	Provide agritourism training for local entrepreneurs	Medium term	MUC y MAC
Agro-Food Route			
1	Enhance accessibility of rural roads and signage	Short term	Local government, CCS directors
2	Certify agroecological and citrus products	Medium term	Producers, MDD
3	Integrate commercial links with local markets and tourism sector	Medium term	Producers, MAD
Livestock Route			
1	Secure financing for roads, livestock infrastructure, and reservoirs	Short term	Local government, BANDEC/BPA Bank, farm owners
2	Provide technical training in sustainable livestock, agroecology, and rural tourism	Medium term	MUC, SCC associations, MAC
3	Promote integration among local	Short term	Producers, MDD,

	actors and strategic partners for joint commercialization		local government
4	Diversify activities (handicrafts, gastronomy, agroecology) to increase income	Medium term	Cultural institutions, youth and women, producers
5	Position the livestock route as a specialized destination in sustainable livestock	Long term	MAC, municipal radio, social media managers

The priority given to the Livestock Route responds to its greater needs for financing, training, and integration among actors, which will allow overcoming current limitations and maximizing its contribution to local development. At the same time, the planned actions for the Agro-Livestock Route and the Agro-Food Route reinforce productive diversification, cultural identity, and municipal competitiveness. Thus, monitoring these actions ensures that agritourism routes are consolidated as a continuous improvement strategy, capable of revitalizing the rural economy, strengthening municipal autonomy, and positioning Calixto García as a benchmark in sustainable and inclusive territorial development.

This plan is conceived in alignment with current agrarian and local development policies, such as the National Economic and Social Development Plan until 2030, the Guidelines of Economic and Social Policy, and Decree 33/2021 on Territorial Development. In this way, the proposed actions not only respond to immediate needs for infrastructure, training, and commercialization but also integrate into public strategies aimed at productive diversification, environmental sustainability, and territorial competitiveness. In particular, agrarian policies recognize the importance of diversifying agricultural activities, fostering community participation, and leveraging endogenous resources as the basis for sustainable development. Therefore, the continuous improvement plan is articulated as a practical complement to these policies, ensuring that agritourism routes effectively contribute to the economic, social, and environmental strengthening of Calixto García municipality.

Feedback and Control System To ensure sustainability, a feedback system must be designed to collect information on customer satisfaction—both internal and external—as well as other control methods to detect errors in the application of the instrument or changes in customer demands. The following recommendations are proposed:

1. Maintain updated customer databases to detect new interests, tastes, and preferences.
2. Monitor and engage tourists via social media and communication channels, taking into account their complaints and suggestions for continuous product improvement.
3. Implement customer satisfaction surveys to gather feedback on complaints, suggestions, and experiences during product enjoyment, including personalized post-consumption attention.
4. Maintain permanent technological and competitive surveillance to detect new product designs or commercial actions by competitors, as well as global trends and the use of new technologies applied to agritourism.

V. Conclusions

The study confirms that agritourism routes constitute an effective strategy to contribute to local development and revitalize the rural economy, as they diversify agricultural production, generate income, preserve peasant cultural identity, and reduce socioeconomic inequalities in harmony with the environment. The methodological instrument developed, consisting of three stages and seven steps, demonstrated its validity by integrating socioeconomic indicators and indices that allow for both objective and qualitative measurement of the contribution of agritourism routes to local development, providing a structured and replicable framework.

The practical application of the instrument in Calixto García municipality corroborated the fulfillment of the general objective of the research, by verifying that the articulation of farms into agritourism routes increases socioeconomic benefits and strengthens municipal autonomy. The theoretical contribution lies in the integration of territorial planning methodologies and endogenous development studies into a single instrument.

The prediction of the object's behavior indicates that, with financing, training, and integration among actors, agritourism routes—especially the livestock route—can be consolidated as competitive and sustainable products, thereby contributing to local development in the medium and long term.

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